

History of the Foundation of the Indian Chemical Society*

A brief account of the antiquity of the chemical studies and technology in India

J. N. MUKHERJEE
Calcutta

INTRODUCTION

AN account of the foundation of the Indian Chemical Society should be preceded by a brief reference to the development of chemical studies since the earliest times when records of these archaeological, linguistic and other sources, are available.

When we were young we heard it stated repeatedly in words as well as in writing that the Hindus had shown some proficiency in literature and in mystic philosophy, the logic of which was difficult to understand: but they have showed no proficiency in the sciences. Civilization in India was considered to have begun after the Achaemenian Empire extended upto the Panjab and the invasion of the Greek warrior Alexander. There is no reference by any Indian writer to the aggression of Alexander. But European historians say that he wanted to attack the Magadh Empire, but his troops rebelled because of attacks of dysentery. Real reasons seem to be that he met with such stiff resistance that he was himself very seriously wounded. These facts are not given any prominence by European writers of the History of India, nor any importance given to the fact that Seleucus Nicator, one of the five generals of Alexander who divided between themselves his empire and became king of territory bordering upon the North-West of India was conquered by Chandra Gupta, the grand father of Asoka. Chanakya, one of the greatest early economists and author of the Law of Kautilya, was the minister of the then emperor of Magadha, Chandra Gupta, called as Chandrakotas by the Greeks, said that foreign kingdom at the border must not be allowed to exist and Seleucus was defeated in the battle and Helen his daughter was given in marriage to Chandra Gupta. It was considered that the history of a civilization should be considered to begin with a written record, for example Buddhist writings and Asokan edicts.

It was the excavation by Daya Ram Sahni at Harappa in 1921 and R. D. Banerjee at Mahenjodaro during 1922-23 and followed up by Vats, Dikshit, Marshall, Hargreaves, Mackay and Majumdar, that led to the exciting discovery of the Harappan culture. European scholars were at first of the opinion that this Harappan culture came from Mesopotamia, on the other hand there is plenty of

evidence that the cultures of the Vedic Aryans were transferred to Mesopotamia by persons who went for business or other purposes from India. It is indeed very strange that Mitannis, whose Gods and hymns were the same as those of the Vedic-Aryans, established "a powerful kingdom in the second half of the 16th century B. C." (Vedic Aryans, J. N. Talukdar I. C. S. (Retd.) "I had conquered Assyria and ruled over practically the whole of upper Mesopotamia and northern Syria, from the East of the Tigris to the Mediterranean coast, with its capital in the Khabur Valley. They were a small aristocracy ruling over a predominantly Hurrian population." "It successfully stopped two of the most powerful pharaohs (1450-1525 B. C.) on the bank of the Euphrates. It then entered into matrimonial alliances with Egypt, as a new menace of resurgent Hittite power under the New kingdom was rising on its north western border. Ultimately, the Mitanni kingdom broke up by the attack of king Suppiluliuma of the Hittites on one side and Assyria on the other, at the time of its last king, Tushratta, who was murdered in a palace intrigue." "A portion in the centre was left for Matiwaja", one of the sons of the Mitanni's king. The language of the Hittites was Indo-European or Indo-German and that their language belongs to the "Zentun" group as distinct from the Satam group, both mean hundred, of the Indo-Aryans and the Iranians. Also a fact that is scarcely touched upon even by Indian scholars is that the most important religious festival of the Hittites was the marriage of a God Teshub riding a bull with a Goddess riding a lion, which reminds one of Shiva and Parvati. However, it has not been possible to find from where the Mitannis came, unless it be that some small groups of Vedic-Aryans left India at different periods of time and gradually established a kingdom of their own, existence of which was not known to the Vedic-Aryans. Will this illustrate that all culture, e. g. the Harappan culture, came to India from Mesopotamia, Babylonia etc, which is only a distorted psychology of European scholars of an older age.

They also discarded the evidence in the Vedas, Upanisads, Puranas, Brahmanas, Dharmasastras

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and other sanskrit composition as being only of mythological interest. An example may be given :

"F. E. Pargiter was the first to work on these lists of kings and dynasties and placed the Mahabharata war in 950 B. C. His method was not regarded as convincing. In Sumerian and Babylonian civilisation, such lists of kings in spite of their drawbacks, are now looked upon as important historical materials. Recently another scholar, Professor R. Morton-Smith, has argued that there is a case for Pargiter's method and dependence on the Puranic lists "has far more rationality than an scepticism". He has worked out the dates of Jarasandha and his son Sahadeva, both kings of Magadha and contemporaries of the Pandavas and placed the Mahabharata war in 975 B. C. Independently Jain tradition supports this chronology."

But in recent years the fundamental question of nature has been troubling the front-ranking foreign scientists. In a letter to *Nature* I read in 1949 (may be 1948) Dirac wrote about ether, the concept of which "the scientists discarded after the Michelsons Morlay experiment...and wondered that a particle of millions or billions volts of energy could be created at any time anywhere in the Universe. It is more important that some of our greatest scientists consider that the *Upanishads* and the *Shyankhya* philosophy of Kapila bring us nearer to a correct concept of the Universe. This Vedic mythology has become of greatest importance. In a book entitled "Science and Human Temperament" Schroedinger, one of the founders of wave mechanics after stating that the scientist through his experiments asks nature to give answers. From these little pieces of answers they tried to create concepts of reality. Nature in her infinite mood can give many answers and he concludes that the "Upanishad got a real vision of reality". In a second book "What is life" which I would advise all students to study who are interested in understanding the elements of the Second Law of Thermodynamics, ultimately he comes to the question of chromosomes and genes and he considers that gene is an aperiodic crystal which could multiply... and this is contrary to the Second Law of Thermodynamics. His conclusion in both the books is that facts do not support a purely mechanistic concept of the Universe and the *Upanishads* are right in mentioning that there is a design.

In an article 'The Distinctive Character of Indian Religion', Dr. S. Radhakrishnan remarks Ramkrishna (1836-1886) was in the direct line of rishis of the *Upanishads*. He stated "When I think of the Supreme Being as inactive, neither creating, nor preserving nor destroying, I call him *Brahman* or *Purusha*, the super-personal God. When I think of Him as active, creating, preserving, destroying, I call him *sakti* or *maya* or *prakriti*. But the distinction between them does not mean a difference...The Divine mother and *Brahman* are one. Sree

C. Rajagopalachari has written a book entitled "Ramakrishna Upanishad."

A concise history of science in India edited by D. M. Bose, S. N. Sen and B. V. Subbarayappa should be read by all students of science in order to familiarize themselves with our rich heritage of scientific and technological achievements. European scientists in general have practically no knowledge of these achievements. Our scientists should be in a position when occasion arises to correct this widespread impression among European scholars, who did not take into consideration this large volume of information because they consider civilization to begin with written records whereas earlier Sanskrit composition were transmitted from generation to generation by mouth with great care to maintain authenticity of the words of the texts and pronounce them correctly.

References to astronomy, mathematics, medicine and other sciences are found in the Vedas, *Upanishads*, *Puranas*, *Brahmanas*, *Dharmashastras* and other Sanskrit compositions. European scholars considered civilization in India to begin from near about the time of Buddha. The recent archaeological excavations have shown that the Harappan culture occur in as a sequence of earliest cultures in India are quite different from that expected by European scholars from Mesopotamia, Babylonia etc. This reminds me of a remark made by Mr. P. Chaudhuri, known as 'Birbal' in Bengali literary circles, in his monthly paper 'Sabuj Patra' that "when you dig India you find Iran". Dr. Schooner after excavation of Pataliputra remarked that "Iranian architects have planned and constructed the city."

There were three phases of the Indian Stone Age. The old Stone Age sites in Kashmir and Panjab are related to the interglacial period of Late Pleistocene (150000 B.C.), the Middle Stone Age cultures flourished around 25000 B.C, while the Late Stone Age emerged definitely during the post-Pleistocene and merged with the Neolithic. 5500 B. C. mark the beginning of Late Stone Age. This is very interesting, as the Harappan civilization as also the civilization of the Vedic Aryans seem to come into being after the Late Stone Age. It seems that there was more or less continuous development of human civilization in India, as also exchanges between different races of men were concerned in these cultures. Copper objects are among some of the finds in the pre-Harappan Culture about 2200 B. C. There is also evidence of lead smelting.

The Vedas, *Upanishads* and other sacred texts contain innumerable references to the use of copper, bronze, coal and of herbs in medicinal preparations, treatment of diseases and their cures and in particular astronomy and mathematics as also anatomy and description of plants, animals and physiology of plants, recognition of worms as cause of human diseases. *Rigveda* mentions the use of metal including gold. "The general term used for the metal is *ayas* which might have meant copper, bronze or lead. There is no

doubt that later the word *ayas* began to mean "iron." "The Vedic people believed that gold possessed supernatural powers." There is nothing against the idea that the Vedic-Aryans were not familiar with iron and its elementary metallurgy at a much earlier part of the second millennium B. C. No notice seems to have been taken of the fact that iron used to be manufactured by the tribes and this practice has continued till recently. Melting of iron must have been known since the earliest. However, the Iron pillar of Delhi, which is of 24'3" in height and weighs more than six tons, would be impossible to manufacture even at present in most countries of the world. The probable date of this pillar is about 400 A.D., and since then it has been existing without any rust or signs of decay.

"The Chinese pilgrim, Hiuen Tsang, has given a description of how brass was being extensively used in India at the time of his visit, and spoken of a huge copper image of the Buddha (80 ft in height) and a brass temple being built (height expected to reach 100 ft. or more) by Harsha."

FOUNDATION OF THE INDIAN CHEMICAL SOCIETY

The following account of the early stages of the chemical investigations and studies provides the background of the considerations leading to the establishment of the Indian Chemical Society. A number of medical men were the pioneers of chemical research in India. The active principles of Indian medicinal plants and enormous number of herbs and drugs were examined both chemically and physiologically by a number of medical men.

In this they drew very limitedly upon the traditional knowledge accumulated since the Rigveda and Atharvaveda, which was developed further through centuries culminating in the work of Charaka and Susruta. The development of chemical processes, such as extraction of alkalies, preparation of alkalies from ashes of plant products and also inorganic sources, use of lime, alkalies varying in strength which were categorised, preparation of salts, development and use of the processes of filtration, precipitation, sublimation, distillation and preparation of drugs for the cure of specific diseases were described. This gives a bare outline of some of the earlier Indian chemical work. Since the earliest times the anatomical description of plants (medicinal and herbs in particular) and studies of their physiology were also carried out. The concise History of Science in India referred to earlier should be consulted by all those interested in Indian achievements in the field of science, chemical technology, metallurgy and other technologies and medicine as also surgery.

The following account has been taken from the 'Silver Jubilee' number of the Indian Chemical Society published in 1948.

"Pioneering systematic work was carried out by Dr. W.B.O. Shaughnessy, Professor of Chemistry, Medical College, Calcutta on the chemical and physiological properties of a large number of Indian herbs and drugs and the results were published in the "Bengal Pharmacopoea" in 1840. Similar work was carried out by some others of the medical profession as also by non-medical persons.

Dr. D. Waldie determined the monthly changes in the salinity of the water of the upper layers of the river Hooghly, in Calcutta in 1854. This work is being continued and should be continued more thoroughly even at the present day.

Dr. Kanailal Dey also worked in 1860 on the medicinal plants of Bengal. Systematic work on modern lines was, however, first initiated in 1875 by Dr. Alexander Pedler, then Professor of Chemistry in the Presidency College, Calcutta in collaboration with Chandra Bhusan Bhaduri. He examined and reported on the coal gas and water supplies of Calcutta. The studies on 'cobra venom' were carried out by him in collaboration with Babu Pulin Behari Soor and published in the Proceedings of the Royal Society of London."

However, Dr. Aghore Nath Chattopadhyay was the pioneer who undertook modern chemical research and obtained in 1875 the degree of Doctor of Science in Chemistry from the Edinburgh University. Illustrious Dr. Sarojini Naidu was his daughter. At the invitation of Prof. Prafulla Chandra Ray he came to the chemistry laboratory of the Presidency College Calcutta in 1914 (?) where he was asked to meet the research chemists working in the laboratory of Prof. Prafulla Chandra Ray. He was of short stature and had a dark complexion. At that time he spoke to us of nothing but the preparation of gold from mercury by the use of extracts from herbs. Prof. Prafulla Chandra Ray told us that when he met Prof. Van't Hoff, the pioneer founder of Physical Chemistry, in Amsterdam he spoke highly of the intelligence of Dr. Aghore Nath Chattopadhyay whom he had met earlier.

Prof. Prafulla Chandra Ray also got the degree of Doctor of Science in chemistry from the University of Edinburgh. He wrote a book on the effect of the British rule and the ruin of industries in Bengal, and also its general demoralising effect. This created a sensation and John Bright, a famous British statesman wrote to the *Times* that Britain should make note of the fact that 'eyes of Indians are being opened'. This book created a strong prejudice against him amongst the British officers in Bengal. He was appointed a lecturer in Chemistry in 1889 in the Presidency College, Calcutta. He engaged himself solely in chemical research since 1894 onwards and attracted a devoted band of workers in chemistry around him, which formed a nucleus of a school of chemistry. His publication on mercurous nitrite which appeared in the *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal* drew the attention of *Nature*, in which the following comments were made: "The *Journal of the*

Asiatic Society of Bengal can scarcely be said to have a place in our chemical libraries. The current number however, contains a paper by Dr. Prafulla Chandra Ray of the Presidency College, Calcutta, on mercurous nitrite, that is worthy of note." Prof. Prafulla Chandra Ray was also the pioneer founder of chemical industry in India, having established the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works near Calcutta. Sulphuric acid, nitric acid etc. and some salts including magnesium sulphate were some of the lines of manufacture. A speciality was preparation of extracts from medicinal plants as described in Charaka and Susruta. The strength was standardized on the basis of total alkaloid content.

The formation of the Indian Science Congress Association in 1914 as a result of the joint efforts of Professor McMahon, Professor of Chemistry, Canning College, Lucknow and Prof. J. L. Simonsen, Professor of Chemistry, Presidency College, Madras marked a definite stage in the progress of science in India. The association provided a meeting ground of scientists in India of different disciplines at its annual congress. Research works were read and discussed and abstracts were published in the Proceedings of the Congress and also full papers were published in some foreign journals and in the journal of Asiatic Society Bengal.

The establishment of the post graduate Council of Science and the University College of Science by Sir Ashutosh Mookerjee, and the appointment of brilliant men like Chandra Sekhar Venkata Raman, Sarbapalli Radhakrishnan and a very talented batch of younger men created an atmosphere of research in different scientific disciplines including chemistry. Under the initiative and inspiration of Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya, Benares Hindu University was established with chairs in different branches of science including chemistry. At that time research in chemistry on modern lines was also being carried out in several centres, e.g. Lahore, Madras, Agra, Bombay and Bangalore.

By 1919 it was felt by some Indian chemists at their meetings during the sessions of the Science Congress that research publication of Indian chemists were scattered in different foreign journals and it was not possible to have an integrated idea of the work done by Indian chemists as also of their number.

The question of providing a common meeting ground of research chemists in India through a permanent organisation was being discussed by some. There was also support for the publication of results of chemical research in foreign journals as their work would be more widely known. On the other hand some Indian chemists felt that their papers were not welcome by foreign chemical journals and they were not happy about the reasons given for not publishing them. A point was also raised that there would not be a sufficient number of articles for publication in an Indian Journal of Chemistry. Some

Indian chemists, however felt strongly by 1919 that an Indian Chemical Society should be formed, but the question of publication of journal should precede. This involved expenditure and it was not certain how this could be met. So the question was left in a nebulous state.

At the University College, London, Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar, Jnan Chandra Ghosh and Jnanendra Nath Mukherjee took up research work in October 1919 in the Physical Chemistry Laboratory, which was then under Prof. F. G. Donnan, F. R. S. and Foreign Secretary of the Royal Society, London. The question of foundation of an Indian Chemical Society with a journal of its own was discussed, and on the basis of previous conversation each of them had with fellow chemists in India they thought that the foundation of the Indian Chemical Society with a journal of its own would receive almost wholehearted support from Indian chemists. This discussion has been referred to by Prof. Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar in his Presidential address in 1928 to the Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress at Calcutta, as follows :

"I crave your indulgence for a few minutes to disclose the account of a private conference which Dr. Ghosh, Dr. Mukherjee and I had in the year 1919 in the University College Chemical Laboratories in London. The subject-matter of our conference was the starting of an All India Chemical Society, with Sir P. C. Ray as its first President. We had a long discussion on the subject and afterwards we took Professor Donnan into our confidence and he fully approved of the plan. On our return to India out of the many plans which we made together and of all of which Dr. J. N. Mukherjee was to be the custodian, the one which he did not forget to carry out was the founding of the Indian Chemical Society. The President and the Secretary constitute the life and soul of a learned society and if one of them happens to be a colloidal chemist, the success of the Society is by tradition ensured. Take, for example, the case of the Chemical Society, London, which we all recognise as the parent of our Indian Chemical Society. The first President of that Society was Thomas Graham, the father of Colloidal Chemistry. By a curious chance Dr. Mukherjee, who is the first Secretary of the Indian Chemical Society happens to be the father of Colloidal Chemistry in our country, and may we hope from this that our Society will have as glorious and distinguished a record as the parent Society in London, early discussions for whose establishment were also held in the University College Chemical Laboratories in London."

On our return from London a proposal for the establishment of the Indian Chemical Society with a journal of its own was made by Prof. Nil Ratan Dhar who was the President of the Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress held in Madras in 2nd/3rd January, 1922. A Committee was approved consisting of the following to take steps for giving

effect to the resolution :

Dr. Caldwell
 Dr. B. B. Dey
 Dr. R. L. Dutt
 Dr. G. J. Fowler
 Mr. Moudgill
 Dr. J. N. Mukherjee
 Dr. K. G. Naik
 Dr. S. K. Singh
 Dr. J. L. Simonsen
 Dr. E. R. Watson (Convener)

The Committee was later designated as the Executive Committee with Dr. E. R. Watson as the President and myself as the Secretary.

A Sub-Committee was also formed and the members were asked to meet in the same evening. The following were elected as members of the sub-committee :

Dr. E. R. Watson (President)
 Dr. J. L. Simonsen
 Dr. R. L. Dutt
 Dr. J. N. Mukherjee, (Convener and Secretary)

Dr. N. R. Dhar was appointed a member of both the committees by the Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress.

The sub-committee unanimously resolved that the Indian Chemical Society be established and a publication of a journal of the Society be undertaken.

The sub-committee also empowered me to take all necessary steps in this connection.

Prof. J. L. Simonsen said at the meeting that "now that we have passed a resolution we have got a Society", but after the meeting he assured Dr. J. N. Mukherjee that he will give all necessary help. Simonsen said at the meeting that the publication of a journal will be a costly venture and would require about Rs. 20,000/- per annum, which I thought was ridiculous and an attempt to frighten us from the project of publication of a journal. He therefore suggested that the journal be published as a part of the Proceedings of the Asiatic Society of Bengal. But the proposal did not go further. In fact it was considered that the Asiatic Society of Bengal will not be able to contribute financially or give any help in the matter of publication of the journal.

On my return to Calcutta I took up the work of the foundation of the Society in right earnest. At first Dr. Watson had to meet all expenses regarding correspondence etc. out of his own pocket, but later on it was made good from fellowship subscription.

I approached Sir Ashutosh Mookerjee, then

Vice-Chancellor, Calcutta University who wrote on my application to the University of Calcutta that the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society will be published at the University Press, Calcutta at a cost not exceeding Rs. 1,500/-. The formal sanction of the University was communicated by the Registrar, Calcutta University in his letter dated 9. 5. 22.

Dr. Jnan Chandra Ghosh conveyed the decision of the Dacca University, in his letter dated 7th April 1922, sanctioning a grant of Rs. 200 for the purpose.

The Universities of Allahabad and Punjab offered to make an annual contribution of Rs. 200/- and Rs 100/- respectively.

At the meeting of the Sub-Committee and of the Committee held at the Medical College, Lucknow on January 11, 1923 it was resolved that "the Sub-Committee are of opinion that the funds promised will enable a Chemical Society to be started and publish a quarterly journal."

The Society was registered on May 9, 1923 with Dr. P. C. Ray as its Founder President and myself as its Secretary. The composition of the first Council of the Society is given below :

The Members of the Council and Office-bearers in 1924,

President : Sir P. C. Ray, C.I.E., Ph. D., D. Sc.
 Vice-Presidents : Dr. J. L. Simonsen, D.Sc., F.I.C., F.A.S.B.
 Dr. Gilbert J. Fowler, D.Sc., F.I.C.
 Hony. Secretary : Dr. J. N. Mukherjee, D.Sc.
 Hony. Treasurer : Dr. P. C. Mitter, M.A., Ph.D.

Members of the Council :

Dr. S. S. Bhatnagar, D.Sc.
 Dr. B. K. Singh, D.Sc.
 Dr. A. R. Norman, M.A., B.Sc., Ph.D.
 Dr. J. C. Ghosh, D.Sc.
 Dr. K. G. Naik, D.Sc.
 Dr. H. K. Sen, D.Sc.
 Dr. H. E. Annett, D.Sc.
 Dr. B. B. Dey, D.Sc.
 B. H. Wilson,
 Dr. A. N. Meldrum, D.Sc.
 R. N. Sen,
 Dr. R. L. Datta, D.Sc.

Hony. Editors :

Dr. E. R. Watson, D.Sc.
 Dr. N. R. Dhar, D.Sc.

By 1924 the Society had registered on its roll one hundred and one Fellows. The quarterly journal of the Society was first published in November, 1924.

The comments of the referees were pretty, often resented by the authors and the editor had a difficult task of peacemaking. Dr. A. N. Meldrum of Agra was made first Editor, who always used to remark that being a Christian he would turn the other cheek when he would receive a slap on the one.

However, the level of the publications of the Society was fairly high. The *Nature* commented as follows, under the caption 'Chemistry in India':

"The great work in chemistry which has occurred in the Indian Empire during the past ten years, had led to the establishment of an Indian Chemical Society; the first number of the Quarterly journal of the Society has now appeared. Hitherto chemical papers emanating from India have been published either in the Journal of the Chemical Societies of London or America, or in one or other of the larger continental publications. The disadvantages attaching to this procedure became more and more obvious as the volume of new work increased; because the older Journals are becoming overburdened and the need for economy of space necessitated frequent correspondence between authors and editors, entailing grave loss of time in the cases of countries so far distant as India.

"Apart, therefore, from the pleasure with which all British chemists will welcome this national effort on the part of India, there will be general agreement among them that the scheme of decentralisation of publications within the British Empire which it implies is the only one which lead to the rapid and adequate publication of new knowledge and tend ultimately to the real advancement of chemistry.

"The new Journal is a welcome illustration of the development which has taken place in Indian Chemistry during recent years. There are thirteen papers, and only one of these is published under English names. The remaining papers are published by Indians and come from all parts of the Indian Empire. Four of these emanate from the College of Science, Calcutta, and this is as it should be, because, for many years past, this institution has been the back-bone of chemical research in India. The other communications come from Allahabad, Baroda, Dacca, Cuttack, Benares and Madras and constitute a series of which the organising committee, the editor have every reason to be proud."

The Society also established exchange relation with the following journals:

Journal de Chimie Physique, Paris
Chemical Abstract (Journal of the American Chemical Society)

The journal was converted into a bimonthly one in 1928 and into a monthly journal since 1930.

I received two letters—one from Prof. J. C. Philips of the Imperial College of Science and Technology, London, who suggested that separate journal for the Indian Chemical Society was not necessary, as most of the papers contributed by Indian chemists were being published in the Journal of the Chemical Society, London, and the other from (Sir) Martin Foster, Director of the Indian Institute of Science at Bangalore, who made the same suggestion.

The progress made by the Society during the few years of my Secretaryship is illustrated by the following figures:

	1924	1929
No. of Fellows	101	393
No. of subscribers	15	98
No. of exchange journals	10	93
No. of papers published	23	106

To begin with, the Society had no house of its own and I had to accommodate the office of the Society in my sitting room in the University College of Science and Technology, 92, Upper Circular Road, Calcutta. The issue of the journal published by the Society began to pile up in the library of the Department of Chemistry of the University College of Science which had very little space. Sir P. C. Ray then came forward and made a gift of Rs. 10,000/- to the Calcutta University for building a house for the Society. This happily resulted in 1933 in the construction of two large rooms, each of size 30 ft. x 20 ft., along with the verandah and side rooms in the third storey of the extension of the south wing at the University College of Science and Technology, Calcutta for the use of the Society at a nominal token rent of Re. 1/-per month."

In 1929 Prof. H. K. Sen succeeded me as the Secretary of the Society and I was elected a Vice-President.

Other active centres of chemical research being at long distances from Calcutta, the headquarters of the Society, it is obviously not possible for Fellows from these centres, distributed all over India, to attend the meeting of the Society. Arrangements were, therefore, made for opening branches of the Society at those centres of research activities. Soon after the establishment of the Society in 1924, three such branches were opened, one in Lahore in 1925, one in Bombay in 1926 and another in Madras in 1927.

Occasional grants have been received from the Government of India, Government of West Bengal, the Government of Burma and Government of Madras as also from States of Baroda and Hyderabad. Substantial contributions were also being received from time to time from many chemical firms, of which the Alembic Chemical Works, Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works, and the Calcutta Chemical Works deserve particular mention.

The choice of President of the Society was a difficult affair as claims from many persons were being received. But there was no difficulty in declaring Prof. Prafulla Chandra Ray as the first President and he was also designated as founder President in recognition of and a tribute to his pioneering services in chemical research in India. He had however no active part in the foundation of the Society.

Names of Presidents and Editors of the journal during my tenure of office as secretary are given below :

Hony. President	Hony. Editors	Years
Professor P. C. Ray	Prof. N R. Dhar Prof. A.N. Meldrum	} 1924-26
Prof. Gilbert John Fowler	Prof. S S. Bhatnagar Prof. B.K. Singh	

The Indian Chemical Society and its journal are now full grown adults and got themselves established. But we must not forget that stagnation means decay. It is very welcome that some of our fellows have shown interest in chemical education and in apparatus and instruments for equipping schools and colleges for teaching of chemistry as also in the manufacture of sophisticated instruments for which we are dependent on foreign countries. Interchange of information and technics and even finished instruments should continue, for no country should remain isolated from the main stream of development in these spheres. Our Government must undertake directly the manufacture of the most sophisticated instruments. The establishments at Chandigarh and at Calcutta undoubtedly render great service in their respective fields, but a larger portion of activities in this field remain uncovered. The other question, which should trouble us, is to provide in the Headquarter a building with library along with reading room, sanitary arrangements and residential accommodation for about a dozen chemists as representative of different branches of the society. Besides centres like Bombay, Pune, Delhi, Madras, Bangalore, Agra, Patna, Gauhati, Bhubaneswar, in fact all the cities have been flouri-

shing. These branches should provide accommodation for holding seminars and have also well-equipped laboratory and arrangement for meals. It is the urgent duty of the Department of Science & Education and of the Planning Commission to look into requirements of all learned scientific societies established by the devotion of both non-official and official scientists and provide sufficient funds to enable scientists to hold seminars or symposium in different parts of the country. Hundreds of crores of rupees are being spent on many projects, the importance of which cannot be compared with that of development of Science and Technology. We have not yet got a real Science Policy. A National Research Foundation should be formed and accommodated in a building contiguous to the National Science Academy so that they can make use of the common facilities. The National Research Foundation, as in America, Canada and Japan, should have top-most men representing different learned scientific societies as also selected by their own merit to consider the problems of development of science and also of policy for science i.e. application of science and technology for the national welfare.

DEVELOPMENT OF ALL ACTIVITIES RELEVANT TO THE NATIONAL PROGRESS AND ITS WELFARE

It is a pity that often there is some item of research or investigation which is repeated periodically in newer institutions with different names. We are perhaps inducting the phenomena of order and disorder in our planning and planned development of science and technology and in their education in spite of many seminars and symposium, committees and reports on the working of different official scientific institutions. But where is the coordination and coordinated guidance with minimum loss of time and energy and waste of time of scientific personnel. Concrete instances come to my mind, but the article has already become very lengthy. I only hope that the suggestions I have made will be of more value to the Indian chemists and perhaps to scientists in other disciplines. Faith in achievements of our people stretching over four thousand years which have been shared by all sections, caste, creeds etc. of our people, and those who have not yet participated to work in this field will be able to decide what should to be our national Science Policy.